

DEVELOPING COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF CADETS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

Article deals with the methods of developing of cognitive activity of cadets in the process of teaching English. There was indicated the importance of developing of cognitive of cadets and worked out the exercises directed to the developing of cognitive activity. Given educational games can serve for developing of cognitive activity of cadets.

Key words: developing of cognitive activity, effectiveness of the educational games, specialized teaching, increasing of interest of cadets.

ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИ ДАРСЛАРИДА КУРСАНТЛАРНИНГ БИЛИШ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ МУАММОЛАРИ

Аннотация

Мақола инглиз тили дарсларида курсантларнинг билиш фаоллигини ошириш муаммоларига бағишланган. Олий ўқув юрти курсантларининг билиш фаоллигини оширишнинг аҳамияти кўрсатилиб, билиш фаоллигини ошириш бўйича ўқув-топшириқлари ишлаб чиқилган. Ишлаб чиқилган замонавий ўқув-топшириқлари курсантларнинг билиш фаоллигини оширишга хизмат қилади.

Таянч сўзлар: билиш фаоллигини ошириш, инглиз тили ўқитишда ўйин-топшириқларининг самарадорлиги, ихтисосий ўқитиш, курсантларнинг қизиқишини ошириш.

Шахсни ҳар томонлама ривожлантиришда унинг билиш фаоллигини ошириш алоҳида ўрин тутади. Бу эса, ўқитиш усуллари ва воситаларини тўғри танлай олиш билан боғлиқ бўлиб, ўқитувчилардан юксак маҳорат талаб қилади. Шунинг учун ҳар бир ўқитувчи чет тил ўқитиш методикасидан пухта билимга эга бўлиши зарур. Дарсларнинг сифатини ошириш ва курсантларнинг инглиз тилига бўлган қизиқишини оширишга хизмат қиладиган ўйин-топшириқларнинг аҳамияти каттадир. Улардан мисол келтирамиз:

Vocabulary game

“Back to the Board”. Miming Game. The game helps cadets to describe vocabulary and specific structures or collocations by using actions, gestures and body language. The process of the game: Cadets are divided into two teams. One player from each team comes to the front of the class and sits with their back to the board. When teacher says “go” the two teams start miming the first collocation to the player sat at the front of the class. The first player to correctly guess the collocation scores a point for their team. The two teams then mime the second collocation and so on. For example: jump over the low wall, run across the log, climb up the cargo net and so on.

When all three collocations have been guessed correctly, two new players come to the front and three new collocations are written on the board. Play continues until everyone has had a turn guessing mimes. The team with the most points at the end of the game wins.

Grammar game

"Catch". Verb game. Teacher can use this game to help cadets practice using verbs in a variety of tenses or revise verb forms. Cadets should stand in a circle and start the game by throwing a ball to a cadet. As a cadet throws the ball, says a verb in its base form. For example, "to salute". The cadet who catches the ball must say the past, past participle, plural or "-ing" form of the verb, depending on which form a teacher wants the cadets to practice. For example: "saluted, saluting". The cadet then calls out a new verb as they throw the ball to another cadet and so on. If a cadet fails to say the correct verb form, they are out of the game and must sit down. The game can be restarted with a new verb. If a teacher wants to make the game harder, he could ask the cadets to say a sentence using the verb in a particular tense. For example: "Subordinates saluted their superiors at the meeting yesterday." Cadets could also spell the verb form.

Pronunciation game

"Minimal Pairs Bingo". Focus on sounds. A Bingo card commonly has 5*5 squares, so you can use 25 words which are related to military sphere. Teacher should not let the cadets mark their cards. He should provide markers such as small stones or sunflower seeds that they can put on each word as they hear it. The first cadet to get five markers in a row in any direction calls "Bingo!". Cadets remove their markers and a new game starts with the winner as the new caller. After a game or two the cadets can swap cards to get a different arrangement of military words to look at.

Бу ўйинлар курсантларга билимларни ўзлаштириш, тил материали, яъни лексика, грамматика ва талаффуз кўникма ва малакалари ҳосил қилишларида ёрдам беради ва тилни ўрганишга бўлган қизиқишни оширади.

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